

This document supplements the paper titled “Unified Smart Factory Model: A model-based Approach for Integrating Industry 4.0 and Sustainability for Manufacturing Systems”. The paper is under review.

Supplementary Material S1

The Supplementary Material S1 complements the section 3.1 with OPM and OPL description of Process, Input and Output Material Objects, Input and Output Energy, and Information Equipment agents (Human) and Environment. It also complements the OPM diagram shown in Figure 6.

Figure S1.1: Manufacturing Process classification

Input Material Objects (Raw material, Consumables) is physical.
 Input Material Objects (Raw material, Consumables) consists of Raw material, Parts, Sub-assemblies, Assemblies, Interface, and Consumables.
 Input Material Objects (Raw material, Consumables) zooms into Consumables, Interface, Assemblies, Sub-assemblies, Parts, and Raw material.
 Consumables is physical.
 Consumables exhibits Material name/type, Quality, Cost, EI, Prior processing, Quantity, Type, Name, State, and Usable life.
 Interface is physical.
 Interface exhibits ID, Shape/Geometry/Visual, Weight, Material name/type, Quality, Cost, EI, Prior processing, Quantity, and Interface type.
 Assemblies is physical.
 Assemblies exhibits ID, Weight, Quality, Cost, EI, Prior processing, Quantity, Parts, and Interfaces.
 Parts exhibits Shape/Geometry/Visual, Weight, Material name/type, Quality, Cost, EI, and Prior processing.
 Interfaces exhibits Shape/Geometry/Visual, Weight, Material name/type, Quality, Cost, EI, Prior processing, and Interface type.
 Sub-assemblies is physical.
 Sub-assemblies exhibits ID, Weight, Quality, Cost, EI, Prior processing, Quantity, Parts, and Interfaces.
 Parts is physical.
 Parts exhibits ID, Shape/Geometry/Visual, Weight, Material name/type, Quality, Cost, EI, Prior processing, and Quantity.
 Raw material is physical.
 Raw material exhibits ID, Shape/Geometry/Visual, Weight, Material name/type, Quality, Cost, EI, and Prior processing.

Figure S1.2: Input material objects

Figure S1.3: Output material objects

Equipment is physical.
 Equipment can be Initial or Final.
 Equipment consists of Machine, Hand Tool, Material handling, and Computer system.
 Equipment zooms into Computer system, Material handling, Hand Tool, and Machine.
 Computer system is physical.
 Computer system exhibits ID, Name of Equipment (Major Group 35 OSHA), Equipment Type (Manual, Mechanized, Automated), Manning level, Equipment size/footprint, Power Requirements, Accuracy/Precision, Setup time, Maintenance history/schedules, Cost, Process parameters, and Environmental impacts.
 Material handling is physical.
 Material handling exhibits ID, Name of Equipment (Major Group 35 OSHA), Equipment Type (Manual, Mechanized, Automated), Manning level, Equipment size/footprint, Power Requirements, Accuracy/Precision, Setup time, Maintenance history/schedules, Cost, Process parameters, and Environmental impacts.
 Hand Tool is physical.
 Hand Tool exhibits ID, Name of Equipment (Major Group 35 OSHA), Equipment Type (Manual, Mechanized, Automated), Manning level, Equipment size/footprint, Power Requirements, Accuracy/Precision, Setup time, Maintenance history/schedules, Cost, Process parameters, and Environmental impacts.
 Machine is physical.
 Machine exhibits ID, Name of Equipment (Major Group 35 OSHA), Equipment Type (Manual, Mechanized, Automated), Manning level, Equipment size/footprint, Power Requirements, Accuracy/Precision, Setup time, Maintenance history/schedules, Cost, Process parameters, and Environmental impacts.

Figure S1.4: Equipment description

Human is physical.
 Human can be Initial or Final.
 Human consists of Operator 1, Operator 2, and ... Operator n.
 Human zooms into ... Operator n, Operator 2, and Operator 1.
 ... Operator n is physical.
 Operator 2 is physical.
 Operator 1 is physical.

Figure S1.5: Human description

Figure S1.6: Energy description

Figure S1.7: Input information and feedback description

Environment is environmental and physical.
 Environment consists of Immediate Environment and External Environment.
 Environment zooms into External Environment and Immediate Environment.
 External Environment is environmental.

Figure S1.8: Environment description

Baked Board is physical.
 Baked Board can be at Stack or at Screen Printer.
 at Stack is initial.
 at Screen Printer is final.
 Printed Board is physical.
 Board with Components 1 is physical.
 Loader is physical.
 Loader exhibits Energy Consumed.
 Screen Printer is physical.
 Screen Printer exhibits Energy Consumed.
 Electricity is physical.
 Conveyor is physical.
 Pick & Place 1 is physical.
 Pick & Place 1 exhibits Energy Consumed.
 PCB components is physical.
 Sloder Paste is physical.
 Soldered PCB is physical.
 Pick & Place 2 is physical.
 Pick & Place 2 exhibits Energy Consumed.
 Reflow Oven is physical.
 Reflow Oven exhibits Energy Consumed.
 Loading is physical.
 Loading exhibits Event and Time.
 Event can be Loading or Idle.
 Loading occurs if Program is in existent.
 Loading requires Loader.
 Loading changes Baked Board from at Stack to at Screen Printer.
 Loading consumes Electricity.
 Screen Printing is physical.
 Screen Printing exhibits Time and Event.
 Event can be Idle, Printing, or Cleaning.
 Screen Printing occurs if Program is in existent.
 Screen Printing requires Conveyor and Screen Printer.
 Screen Printing consumes at Screen Printer Baked Board, Electricity, and Sloder Paste.
 Screen Printing yields Printed Board.
 Pick&Place 1 is physical.
 Pick&Place 1 exhibits Event and Time.
 Pick&Place 1 occurs if Program is in existent.
 Pick&Place 1 requires Conveyor and Pick & Place 1.
 Pick&Place 1 consumes PCB components, Printed Board, and Electricity.
 Pick&Place 1 yields Board with Components 1.
 Pick&Place 2 is physical.
 Pick&Place 2 exhibits Event and Time.
 Pick&Place 2 occurs if Program is in existent.
 Pick&Place 2 requires Pick & Place 2 and Conveyor.
 Pick&Place 2 consumes Board with Components 1, PCB components, and Electricity.
 Pick&Place 2 yields Board with Components 2.
 Reflow is physical.
 Reflow exhibits Event and Time.
 Event can be off, maintain, or setup.
 Reflow occurs if Program is in existent.
 Reflow requires Reflow Oven and Conveyor.
 Reflow consumes Board with Components 2 and Electricity.
 Reflow yields Soldered PCB.

Figure S1.9: OPL representation of PCB assembly line (compliments Figure 6)